

NUTRI-KNOW

Farmer's
Encyclopedia
on innovative
Nutrient
Management
Solutions

EIP-AGRI
Operational Group
Biorefinery Glás

Biorefinery Glás

Biorefinery Glás: Techno-Economic Analysis

<https://biorefineryglas.eu/>

Activities

- Demonstrating a small-scale mobile grass biorefinery on multiple farms in South West Ireland.
- Producing and validating multiple products from grass through biorefining, including an improved fodder press-cake fibre for cattle, protein concentrate feed for monogastrics, high-value prebiotic sugars (for the food and feed markets) and recovery of nutrients for use as fertiliser.
- Facilitating bioeconomy knowledge exchange activities with Irish farmers.
- Delivering an extensive dissemination package, including digital storytelling, with farmers playing a central role.

Further details

Total budget: € 940.498,00

Main funding source: Rural development 2014-2020 for Operational Groups

Rural Development Programme: 2014IE06RDNP001 - Ireland Rural Development Programme (Regional)

The project has ended, but the biorefinery technology is being implemented at a pilot scale on a farm in Kerry

South-West, Ireland

**Munster Technological University
Kerry, Tralee**

Project coordinator

James Gaffey

james.gaffey@mtu.ie

Objectives

This project aims to improve the sustainability, value and resource efficiency of Ireland's agriculture sector through farmer diversification into the bioeconomy. To achieve this, Biorefinery Glás will:

- demonstrate a replicable small-scale biorefinery with Irish farmers, which integrates easily into Ireland's existing agricultural structures;
- improve agricultural resource efficiency through on-farm biorefining to produce value-added products and increase protein availability;
- reduce greenhouse gas emissions associated with manure and feed imports;
- drive new bioeconomy value-chain development and demonstrate business models that offer diversification opportunities for farmers.

Fresh cut grass is loaded onto the hopper on the biorefinery

Grass biorefinery crushes and presses grass to produce a solid presscake fraction that can be used as ruminant feed and a protein rich liquid fraction that can be used as a monogastric feed, prebiotic and grass whey fertiliser

Results

Techno-economic analysis (2021) of a next-generation grass biorefinery in West Cork revealed that integrating anaerobic digestion (AD) and producing multiple co-products significantly improves viability.

Scenario 3 (Biorefinery + AD + protein fibre + FOS) showed the best performance with €332,841 profit and a 12% return on capital.

A standalone biorefinery with FOS (Scenario 4) yielded modest returns (€16,017, 3% return).

Scenarios without FOS or AD were unviable, with losses of €352,951 and €375,078.

The plant could meet 25% of poultry, 5% of pig protein and 12% of dairy cow silage feed needs in West Cork, offering meaningful feed substitution.

Feedstock cost, energy efficiency, and product pricing were key drivers of viability.

The analysis demonstrates the importance of product diversification and energy integration for financial feasibility.

Context

To support Ireland's bioeconomy and GHG targets, an economic analysis of the next generation of stationary biorefinery was proposed for West Cork, collocated with existing industrial sites for synergies in logistics, feedstock sourcing, and energy use.

The plant requires 8 tons of fresh grass per hour over 210 days, supplemented by silage over 70 days. Two production pathways were examined: basic (protein concentrate + press-cake) and extended (adding FOS refinement).

The land requirement was 500–600 ha/year with high-yield grass (12–14 t DM/ha). Feedstock could be sourced locally with minimal disruption to existing uses. Land use substitution in a 15km radius of the plant was estimated at 1%. Energy demands are high (35 kWh/t power, 55 kWh/t heat), making AD integration crucial- which can reduce energy costs from 20% to 10%. Capital costs were substantial but not the main barrier; feedstock price and product value were critical. Sensitivity analysis showed that lowering feedstock cost (from €150/t DM silage and €70/t fresh grass) was necessary for positive returns. The model offers diversification potential for farmers, especially in low-viability regions, with projected farm incomes of €20,000/Labour Unit/year for participants—above current beef farming averages.

Financial analysis of options assessed

	1. Bioref. & AD Prot Conc + protein fibre	2. Bioref. only Prot Conc + protein fibre	3. Bioref. & AD Prot Conc + protein fibre + FOS	4. Bioref. Prot Conc + protein fibre + FOS
Grass Biorefinery Pathways				
Total capital expenditure	€ 3,290,000	€ 1,670,000	€ 3,450,000	€ 1,805,000
Total O&M expenditure	€ 1,693,493	€ 1,689,428	€ 1,741,649	€ 1,713,598
Total Revenues	€ 1,445,889	€ 1,421,739	€ 2,190,794	€ 1,815,338
Profit/Loss before tax	-€ 352,951	-€ 375,078	€ 332,841	-€ 16,017
Return on Capital	-9%	-18%	12%	3%

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